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Start-up challenge report

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RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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Introduction

Light as a tool can increasingly be found in a wide range of products, from high-tech to everyday life objects. Photonics as a cross-sectorial and key enabling technology stands for higher efficiency and innovation potential from engineering to healthcare industries and is able to meet the social and environmental challenges. Therefore, it is important to sustainably support innovation European-wide in the field of optical technologies, by promoting start-up companies and supporting entrepreneurship.

This is what OptecNet Deutschland is working for – providing a basis for a stable and growing photonics business! Therefore, OptecNet Deutschland organised the **European Photonics Start-up Challenge** in the framework of the European Outreach project “Photonics4All” to support innovative business ideas and promote entrepreneurship in photonics and thus, provide a stepping stone for their business.

OptecNet Deutschland e.V. is the federal association of Germany's eight regional optical technologies innovation networks. They work together to support supra-regional and international activities such as international co-operations, technology transfer and innovation promotion, promotion of young talents and PR on a national level.

Motivation

Especially for medium-sized and big companies in photonics, creating disruptive innovations requires an established innovation culture and co-operative innovation processes e.g. from the open innovation approach. Because of difficulties in implementing these issues, many companies co-operate with start-ups or buy them to keep up with ever-shorter innovation cycles. In addition, e.g. photonics students often go the “normal” career path: After finishing their studies, they start working for research institutes or companies, without thinking of creating their own business in photonics.

Simultaneously, start-ups are innovative and growing faster than other companies. Founders are often well educated and on average younger than 35 years old (KPMG German Start-up Monitor 2013-2016: <http://deutscherstartupmonitor.de/>). By now, politics recognize the potential and the importance of those actors for economic growth. Thus, the support of founders and start-ups with new business ideas and models is less a problem of recognition, but more a challenge of implementation. A way would be to go for a risk culture and be more confident in brave and young entrepreneurs.

A start-up challenge supports many of those aspects. With a cash price start-up companies are financially supported e.g. to customize their web presence or purchase new laboratory equipment. Reporting about the challenge and the winners is a helpful marketing activity to promote the technology, service or business model of the start-ups throughout Europe. A public event at a photonics trade fair with marketing pitches supports networking activities in the photonics sector in general, but mainly with potential investors, business angels, customers and co-operation partners in research and development. Furthermore, photonics networks and clusters can further support, coach and consult the start-ups with their services and activities.

In addition, a start-up challenge is able to sensitize and encourage students, young researchers and employees as well as the society in general to found an own company. Such events promote the importance of science, economy and society and stimulate entrepreneurship, support outstanding business models and thus, innovation in photonics.

Organisation

In order to promote start-ups and entrepreneurship in the field of photonics, the Innovation Networks for Optical Technology in Baden-Württemberg, Photonics BW, and in Berlin, Brandenburg OpTecBB, both members of OptecNet Deutschland organised the European Photonics Start-up Challenge with the support of the other regional networks of OptecNet Deutschland and the Photonics4All consortium partners which took place on October, 13th, 2016 in Berlin in the framework of the International Congress “micro photonics”. For communication purposes, the organisers created a logo based on the CI of the Photonics4All project.

European Photonics Start-up Challenge

The stepping stone for your business!

Figure 1 Logo of the Photonics4All Start-up challenge

Photonics BW coordinated the task and OpTecBB looked after the regional issues with the event location, local sponsors and local promotion.

Sponsors acquisition

First, OptecNet Deutschland and the Photonics4All partners looked for sponsors by contacting them directly per phone and chats at events. To support the acquisition, OptecNet Deutschland designed a simple flyer (Annex 2: Sponsoring flyer) with the main information for potential sponsors. Three sponsoring packages were offered:

1. A bronze sponsorship of 1,000 Euros: presentation of company logo on event flyers and promoting websites as well as reference as sponsor in all invitations by email and in all press releases and mentioning during the final pitch event.
2. A silver sponsorship of 2,500 Euros: the sponsor receives a bronze package, which additionally includes a presentation of the company's promotion material and one roll-up display during the event.
3. A premium sponsorship of 5,000 Euros: the premium sponsor receives the silver package, which additionally includes the opportunity of being part of the jury.

For a successful sponsor acquisition, Photonics BW produced a corresponding sponsorship agreement (Annex 3: Sponsorship agreement 1000, Annex 4: Sponsorship agreement 2500, Annex 5: Sponsorship agreement 5000). The

acquisition of sponsors was a difficult task, not because of less interest of the companies, but because of too many other sponsoring activities, the companies are already providing. They have a yearly budget for marketing and a big part of it was already reserved for defined activities. Some companies finally sponsored the event: Nanoscribe GmbH (www.nanoscribe.de) sponsored 1000 Euros; The LUX Photonics Consortium (<http://luxphotonicsconsortium-sg.org>) and Berlin Adlershof (<http://www.adlershof.de/en/>) aka WISTA Management GmbH sponsored 1000 Euros as well. Berlin Partners (<http://www.berlin-partner.de/en/>) sponsored the catering for the final pitch event and Messe Berlin (<http://www.messe-berlin.de/en/>) sponsored the free stage in an exhibition hall. EPIC – European Photonics Industry Consortium (<http://www.epic-assoc.com/>) sponsored the challenge by promoting it on the business network platform LinkedIn. As a media partner, the specialist journal “PHOTONIK” (<http://www.photonik.de/>) with approx. 17,000 copies per edition in Germany, Austria and Switzerland, reported the final event and the innovative technology of the winning start-up. Because of further support by Nanoscribe who promoted the event on his website and with flyers, the Photonics4All Consortium decided to upgrade its sponsorship to a premium one. To financially support the winner, OptecNet Deutschland added 3,000 Euros for the cash price out of the project budget. The objective was to receive sponsorship agreements with a total amount of 10,000 Euros. This objective has been successfully reached.

Award for the winner

The winner of the European Photonics Start-up Challenge has been awarded with a cash price of 6,000 Euros and a coaching package for a value of 1,500 Euros redeemable in the business offers provided by the corresponding Photonics4All partner in Germany, France, Sweden, Austria or the UK (e.g. International market observation, business development, internationalisation, etc.). The coaching package was drafted by the project partners because of the low sponsoring amount. In addition, the winner has been granted with an exclusive professional article in the journal PHOTONIK and broad European-wide reporting in photonics related journals as well as on the project's and partners' websites and in social media. In addition, the winner won a laser engraved cup with the Photonics4All logo in a glass cube and the letters “European Photonics Start-up Challenge – The stepping stone for your business!” as well as the PPPP Logo on the aluminium base.

Figure 2 Award for the winner

Awards for every finalist

The European Photonics Start-up Challenge was dedicated to award start-ups and start-ups' projects throughout Europe. The costs for travelling to the event in Berlin could be a financial burden for young start-ups, the consortium therefore decided to grant every finalist a sum up to 300 Euros for travel expenses per start-up. In addition, the finalists were supported with a three-day trade fair presentation. For interested start-ups, OptecNet Deutschland organised a Business and Technology Tour in the technology park "Centre Berlin Adlershof" on the day following the challenge. In order to visit the exhibition halls of the "micro photonics", the finalists also received visitor codes for all three days.

Promotion of the European Photonics Start-up Challenge

The promotion of the European Photonics Start-up Challenge started in June 2016 with publications on the websites of OptecNet Deutschland and its eight regional innovation networks for optical technologies, Photonics4All and the Photonics4All partners as well as e.g. Swiss photonics and Wallstreet-online. The professional journal "Photonik" and a few start-up platforms also promoted the event on their website. Furthermore, a flyer was developed and disseminated by mail and as a printed version at photonics trade fairs (e.g. Optatec), at working group meetings, information events and via professors and group leaders at universities. Numerous centres for innovation and start-ups and the European funded project ACTPHAST (<http://www.actphast.eu/>) supported the promotion by informing their start-ups and further stakeholders about the start-up challenge.

After the application deadline, the flyer has been updated (Annex 7: Promotion Flyer Update Handout) with the finalists' names and handed out with the programme and a short description of the final pitches as a printed version. During the Pitch Event, a project manager of the micro photonics' team distributed these handouts to visitors rushing along to invite them watching the Pitch Event. The updated flyer has been made downloadable on the different promotion channels such as websites and social media. Furthermore, the start-up challenge has been added in the official trade fair programme, on the micro photonics website and promoted with announcement in the trade fair halls.

Application

Applications were open to representatives of start-ups' projects and companies, service providers and business representatives whose companies are younger than 3 years, generate less than 1 million Euro annual sales in photonics and for those the European Small Business Regulation apply. The application deadline was first set to September 9th, 2016. Later, it was extended to September 16th, 2016 in order to receive more applications. Interested Start-ups were able to apply by sending OptecNet Deutschland the application form (Annex 1: Application Form), a description of their

business idea (max. 5 DIN A4 pages inspired by a business plan) and a brief biography by mail or fax.

Aiming at getting a maximum of eight finalists, the Photonics4All partners assessed the submitted applications. Selection criteria were technical performance, business idea, investment potential and competitive advantage. This procedure has finally been cancelled, because only eight applications have been submitted and each application fulfilled the application criteria and was very innovative.

Event place

The Award Ceremony of the European Photonics Start-up Challenge took place during the international photonics exhibition and conference “micro photonics” (<http://www.micro-photonics.de/en/>) on October 13th, 2016 in Berlin.

During the Exhibition “micro photonics”, a so-called “career lounge” was available in the third exhibition hall (hall 7.2c) to students, apprentices, university graduates and Young Professionals who wanted to get in touch with companies and institutes from the photonics industry, inform themselves about current job offers on a Job wall, test their own “Market Value” and to companies and institutes to get in contact with potential employees from the photonics industry, enhance their corporate image and increase their exposure as a top employer use the Career Lounge as branding tool, provide an insight into the various departments of your company and use the micro photonics to their advantage and get in touch with regional, national, European, and international interested parties. The career lounge was equipped with an audio and light system as well as with a projector. Additionally, two timers were installed to show the audience and the start-ups the left pitch time. The jury was placed in front of the stage at ground level and the audience could take a seat at cube seats. Every visitor and exhibitor was free to watch the event.

Figure 3 3D model of the career lounge with touch points at the front

One of the so-called “touch points” was used by the finalists of the European Photonics Start-up Challenge as a three-day trade fair presentation place. Additionally, the touch point was equipped with a monitor to present the project itself, the innovation offers and requests (IO/IR) (template forms in Annex 9: Innovation Offers and Requests), which were already gathered by the project consortium and to promote the opportunity

to offer or request an innovation. The Photonics4All consortium search then internally for corresponding partners or present the IO/IR(s) at trade fairs, on cluster and project websites as well as in workshops etc. On basis of this innovation board, OptecNet Deutschland promoted the presented IOs and IRs to potential cooperation partners.

Quote: “Over 1,000 participants from 15 countries from all parts of the world attended the first edition of the new trade fair and congress micro photonics in Berlin. From 11th to 13th October, a high-level congress took place alongside the displays of some 80 national and international exhibitors representing micro-optics, microsystem technology and optoelectronics, who showcased their innovative products and services. The next edition of this business and networking event is scheduled for autumn 2017.” (micro photonics press release: <http://www.micro-photonics.de/en/Presse-Service/Pressemitteilungen/index.jsp?lang=en&id=698113>)

Marketing pitches

The finalists presented their business model in short marketing pitches of 3 minutes with 3 slides to the jury and the audience. After the 3 minutes, a time-out slide ended the presentation and the microphone was turned off. Then, the jury could ask questions within 5 minutes to clarify issues they did not understand or missed in the presentation.

During the award ceremony of the European Photonics Start-up Challenge four start-ups from Germany, three from France and one from Austria have pitched their business ideas.

Finalist/Start-up	Photonics Sector/Technology
Sicoya GmbH (Germany)	High-speed Silicon Photonics interconnects in next generation data centres
TeraTonics (France)	Terahertz Sensing
Lilian Labs (Germany)	Water analysis device for everyone
mir sense (France)	Laser based gas sensors
Asaphus Vision GmbH (Germany)	Develop embedded face recognition and gaze estimation software
GreenTropism (France)	Mathematical models and software components for bio spectral analyses
AIXEMTEC GmbH i.G. (Germany)	Automation and assembly of optical systems
Crystalline Mirror Solutions GmbH (Austria)	AlGaAs-based multilayers, in high-performance laser optics

Table 1 List of the finalist of the start-up challenge and photonics technology addressed

Jury

The jury consisted of photonics and business experts and evaluated the business models regarding the specific criteria of technical performance, business idea, innovation potential, competitive advantage and pitch performance. These criteria are the main basic prerequisites to convince investors as well as to survive in the business world. The jury used a table to note each criteria from one to three (one – ok, two –

good, three – very good) for every single start-up. The winner was thus the start-up with the highest sum of notes.

The jury members were Lucille Bonnet (Investment Manager at High-Tech Gründerfonds Management GmbH), Jana Hille (Project Manager at Cube GmbH), Sylvia Kaschke (Editor in Chief at AT-Fachverlag GmbH/PHOTONIK), Olaf Kraft (Head of Sales for OEM business at business unit Industry of Jenoptik Optical Systems GmbH) und Dr Bernd Ludwig (Head of Centre for Photonics and Optics at Wista Management GmbH).

Audience

The Award Ceremony of the European Photonics Start-up Challenge was open to every congress and exhibition visitors. People who were interested in attending the Award Ceremony of the European Photonics Start-up Challenge could register on the website of OpTecBB to receive a one-day free visitor code for the fair micro photonics. Including the representatives of the start-ups and the later mentioned speakers, there were 30 registrations in total. Counting the visitors who were present during the event, the audience consisted of more than 50 people.

Award Ceremony of the European Photonics Start-up Challenge

Corresponding to the agenda (Annex 8: Programme Handout) the Award Ceremony of the European Photonics Start-up Challenge took place on October 13th, 2016 from 1:00 pm to 4 pm at the career lounge (exhibition hall 3 /hall7.2c) of the international trade and congress fair micro photonics in Berlin.

First, Dr Frank Lerch, the moderator of the event from OpTecBB and Johannes Verst from Photonics BW welcomed the start-ups, the jury and the audience. After a short introduction about the objectives and activities of Photonics4All and the programme of the event, Mr. Lerch introduced the five jurors to the audience of more than 50 people and described the rules of the marketing pitches. After every two marketing pitches, a short talk about different important topics for start-ups was held. The last talk was used to evaluate the assessment results.

Figure 4 Dr Frank Lerch, OpTecBB introduced the jury of the final with to the audience of more than 50 photonics experts

The pitch session was open by the German start-up Sicoya GmbH with a presentation of their business idea for a faster internet by Optical Tranceivers for low Costs and Scalable Datacenter Solutions.

Figure 5 Marketing Pitch of Sicoya GmbH

After the 3 minutes pitch of Sicoya GmbH, the jury asked a few questions (max. 5 minutes) to be able to better assess the business idea in terms of the evaluation criteria.

Figure 6 The jury from left to right: Dr Bernd Ludwig (Wista Management GmbH), Sylvia Kaschke (AT-Fachverlag GmbH/PHOTONIK), Lucille Bonnet (High-Tech Gründerfonds Management GmbH), Olaf Kraft (Jenoptik Optical Systems GmbH) and Jana Hille (Cube GmbH)

The second pitch was held by TeraTronics from France about their innovative Terahertz sensing technology for contactless non-destructive single shot testing and biomedical imaging. A 5 minutes questions-answers session followed the 3 minutes pitch.

Figure 7 Questions and answers after the marketing pitch of TeraTronics with Time Out slide in the background

Then, Ms. Lucille Bonnet, Investment Manager of the High-Tech Gründerfonds Management GmbH and also a member of the jury talked about the High-Tech Gründerfonds and possibilities for start-ups in a 10 minutes presentation.

The third pitch was held by the German start-up Lilian Labs, which developed a simple but effective water analysis device for everyone. Again, the jury was invited to ask questions.

The fourth pitch from Mir Sense from France was about laser-based gas sensors for demanding applications.

Figure 8 Pitch of Lilian Labs (left) and mirSense (right)

After the two marketing pitches, Lars Hansen, Head of Charlottenburger Innovation Centre (CHIC) informed the start-ups and the audience about Berlin Adlershof and the special services of Wista Management for start-ups.

The German start-up Asaphus Vision GmbH presented in the fifth pitch their state-of-the-art development of embedded face recognition and gaze estimation software followed by questions and answers.

The sixth pitch from GreenTropism from France presented their mathematical models and software components for bio-spectral analyses with questions and answers of the jury.

Figure 9 Pitch of Aixemtec (left) and Asaphus Vision GmbH (right)

The two pitches were followed by the third talk “Starting a Photonics Company” from the winner of the start-up Challenge at the Optatec 2016 in Frankfurt a.M., Germany, Dr Jürgen Schmied from the GATTAquant GmbH with challenges and tips for starting a company in the field of optical technologies.

Figure 10 Third talk “Starting a Photonics Company”, Dr Jürgen Schmied from GATTAquant GmbH

The AIXEMTEC GmbH i.G. from Germany presented in the seventh pitch session their developed equipment and services for automation and assembly of optical systems.

The eighth and last pitch was held by Crystalline Mirror Solution GmbH from Austria who presented their developed AlGaAs-based multilayers in high-performance laser optics.

These two pitches were followed by questions of the jury as well.

“Founding and Financing High-Tech Start-ups” by Prof Dr Rust from Mock Rechtsanwälte was the fourth talk. Simultaneously, Johannes Verst evaluated the ratings of the jury and prepared the check over 6,000 Euros for the winner after consultation with the jury.

The winner was Sicoya GmbH, second place winner of the German start-up Challenge at the Optatec 2016 in Frankfurt a.M., Germany (<http://www.photonik.de/optatec-2016-nachlese/150/21302/331347>). Sicoya was handed over the laser engraved cup and the check. The coaching will be individually designed in consultation with Sicoya to address their needs.

Second winner was Crystalline Mirror Solutions from Austria and third place winner mirSence from France.

Figure 11 Award ceremony: The winner of the European Photonics Start-up Challenge Sicoya GmbH (middle) and the organizers Johannes Verst from Photonics BW (left) and Dr Frank Lerch from OpTecBB (right) with a roll-up of the premium sponsor Nanoscribe GmbH

After the award ceremony, the start-ups, the jury, the lectures and the audience were invited to discuss the presented topics and network with beverages, sweets, fruits and some other food.

The European Photonics Start-up Challenge addressed all kind of start-ups: service providers and equipment developers as well as young founders with a photonics based business idea and European-wide well-established start-ups. After all, the start-up with the most innovative, the most competitive advantaged with a well-developed business model and good selling skills/pitch performance won the European Photonics Start-up Challenge.

Dissemination

The successful award ceremony of the European Photonics Start-up Challenge was mainly disseminated by reporting about the event and the winner. As mentioned, the media partner Photonik will report about the event and the winner in their upcoming December edition (report draft in Annex 10: Report Draft PHOTONIK) and a longer version will follow. A professional article in a former edition of the PHOTONIK also reported about the winner Sicoya GmbH.

Many international and national reports about the European Photonics Start-up Challenge and the winner Sicoya GmbH have been published:

Press Release of micro photonics

<http://www.micro-photonics.de/en/Presse-Service/Pressemitteilungen/index.jsp?lang=en&id=698113>

SPIE reported in Optics.org

<http://optics.org/news/7/10/28>

LaserFocusWorld

<http://www.laserfocusworld.com/articles/2016/10/micro-photonics-2016-a-new-congress-and-trade-fair-on-biophotonics-and-microoptics.html>

Sicoya GmbH

<http://sicoya.com/de/2016/10/09/sicoya-won-the-european-photonics-start-up-challenge-at-micro-photonics/>

OptecNet Deutschland

<http://optecnet.de/news/detail/european-photonics-start-up-challenge-393/>

Regional networks of OptecNet e.g. Photonics BW

<http://photonicsbw.de/news/detail/european-photonics-start-up-challenge-393/>

LinkedIn Sites of

Nanoscribe GmbH, OptecNet, EPIC, micro photonics, Photonics4All, RespiceSME

Photonics4all

<http://photonics4all.eu/entrepreneurs/start-up-challenge/>

Photonics.com

<http://www.photonics.com/Article.aspx?AID=61266>

Picmagazine.net

https://picmagazine.net/article/100444/Sicoya_wins_European_photonics_startup_challenge

Siliconsemiconductor.net

<http://www.siliconsemiconductor.net/article/100444-Sicoya-wins-European-photonics-startup-challenge.php>

Twitter Channels

Photonics BW, EPIC, Photonics4All

Crystalline Mirror Solutions

<http://www.crystallinemirrors.com/news/>

and on Facebook:

https://www.facebook.com/crystallinemirrors/photos/pb.1663093080638450.-2207520000.1477820466./1808167019464388/?type=3&fb_noscript=1

The December edition of the Photonics BW Journal “InFocus” will also report about the Start-up Challenge and the winner Sicoya GmbH with its brilliant and innovative technology.

Furthermore, OptecNet Deutschland disseminated the business ideas of the finalists in workgroup meetings and the Photonics4All Innovation Workshops (reported in D2.4). In addition to their own news/marketing channels, the start-ups disseminated their successful participation in the award ceremony of the European Photonics Start-up Challenge by participating at different networking activities/events of OptecNet Deutschland and its regional networks.

During the 4th Innovation Workshop, the technology of one of the finalist of the start-up challenge, Asaphus Vision, was conveyed to a Senior developer of the technical centre of Visteon. Visteon is very interested in their eye and head tracking technology and will proof future co-operations to link the technology of Asaphus Vision with their head-up display development. In addition, Prof Dr Schiefer from the Vision Research Competence Centre of the University of Applied Science Aalen will get in touch to Asaphus for a potential co-operation in their project AMPEL – Aalen Mobility Perception & Exploration Lab.

Impact

The European Photonics Start-up Challenge was a great opportunity to support start-ups in terms of finance, marketing, consulting, networking etc. as well as to promote entrepreneurship. Sensitizing the broad photonics community for topics like founding a start-up in photonics and a risk culture was also reached by such a scope in the photonics community. Almost every finalist thanks Photonics4All for the great organisation of giving them a public stage.

At the end of the award ceremony of the start-up challenge, Steve Anderson, Director of Industrial Development at SPIE was inspired by the event and asked OptecNet Deutschland for their support to organize the SPIE start-up challenge at one of the most important trade fairs for optical technologies, the Photonics West. Furthermore, Karl Gedda-Mudroc, General Manager of OpticsValley (a partner in Photonics4All) is thinking about expanding their French photonics start-up challenge to a European one, with the support of OptecNet Deutschland.

Additionally, the start-up challenge at the Optatec event benefits from the experiences and results of the European Photonics Start-up Challenge. Probably, the start-up challenge in 2018 will be shifted to the annual meeting of OptecNet Deutschland, with many exhibitors and a huge framework programme.

Few start-ups considered the marketing impact generated by the challenge more important than any cash prizes, but it also depends on the level of maturity of the start-up. One finalist participated in different working group meetings and one of the first

three innovation workshops of Photonics4All and could establish some very useful connections.

Few start-ups could also link to potential co-operation partners from the other start-ups as well as to the jury and the sponsors. Five confidential partnership agreements for evaluation of further potential interests regarding research, technical and manufacturing co-operations as well as financial and service co-operations were signed. This includes potential co-operations opportunities between French, Austrian and German start-ups.

Furthermore, the contact mediation between the finalist Asaphus Vision GmbH and the company Visteon as well as with the project AMPEL of the University of Applied Science Aalen as described in the last section of the chapter “Dissemination” builds a starting point for sustainable co-operations.

The European Photonics Start-up Challenge had reached a great coverage, with many reports in news media in the field of photonics. The finalists were very happy about the organisation of the challenge, the corresponding support and its results.

Lessons learned

For such an European Photonics Start-up Challenge with a high coverage, the support and promotion of many partners (Photonics4All consortium, micro photonics, the journal Photonik, jurors companies etc.) is a very important issue for success.

Also very important is a well-defined big photonics event like an international trade fair as a host. It is necessary to organise such a ceremony with a big audience e.g. in an exhibition hall. Even in the context of a big event, intensive promotion and active visitor acquisition to reach a big audience is necessary.

For the whole promotion of the challenge, from finding sponsors, start-ups' applications up to the final event, it is crucial to hold a strict timing in order to guarantee the successful implementation of such an event. It is not necessary to start more than 6 months before the event, but finding and acquiring sponsors should start soon enough to ensure the organisation of the challenge.

For the date of the challenge and the time for promotion, it is better to choose a period with few events organised in the field of actions (trade fairs, congresses and start-up challenges) to reach higher quality as well as to find enough sponsors and start-ups.

A well-organised event with engaged partners, enough financial support and connections to many start-ups is a sure-fire success regarding the impact of a start-up challenge.

Annexes

Annex 1: Application Form

OptecNet Deutschland e.V.
represented by
Photonics BW e.V.
Anton-Huber-Str. 20
73430 Aalen
Germany

fax: +49 736173 90 94
email: verst@photonicsbw.de

Application for the European Photonics Start-up Challenge

I / We hereby apply for the European Photonics Start-up Challenge in the framework of the European funded project Photonics4All with my business idea:

title of business idea

title, first name, surname

street, number

zip code, city

country

email

phone

Attachments

- Description of business idea (max. 5 DIN A4 pages inspired by a business plan)
- Biography of applicant (1-2 pages each)

By submitting the application, the modalities of participation are accepted. The participant(s) declare(s) their full authorship of the advertised job and indemnify the OptecNet Deutschland e.V. from and against third party claims. The submitted documents can not be reclaimed. With the purpose-related storage and use of data explained the / participants agree. OptecNet Deutschland e.V. reserves changes and additions to the modalities of participation. The judges' decision is final.

place, date

signature

Annex 2: Sponsoring flyer

European Photonics Start-up Challenge

at International Trade Fair *micro photonics*
on 12 Oct. 2016 in Berlin

Up to 8 Finalists	3 min Marketing Pitches	10,000 Euro
Big Public Audience	Exhibition Space for Start-ups	Support by Photonics Networks

Support Innovative and outstanding business models
in photonics in the framework of the
European project „Photonics4All“.

Be a sponsor and invest in the future of photonics!

Bronze – 1,000 Euro
Presentation of your company logo on event flyers and on promoting websites as well as your company name in invitation emails, press releases and during the event.

Silver – 2,500 Euro
Presentation of your company promoting material and one roll-up display during the event at the fair micro photonics and receive services of bronze package.

Premium – 5,000 Euro
Be a one of five jury members, hand over the award and receive the services of silver package.

	<p>Photonics4All Website: www.photonics4all.eu</p> <p>Contact: verst@photonicsbw.de</p>
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Annex 3: Sponsorship agreement 1000

Pro rata Sponsorship agreement of
„Photonics4All Start-up Challenge“
as part of the fair “micro photonics” on October 11th-13th, 2016 in Berlin.

between (organizer):

OptecNet Deutschland e.V.
Garbsener Landstr. 10
D-30419 Hannover

and (sponsor):

The sponsor receives the following services in return for a pro rata sponsorship in amount of 1,000.00 Euro (one thousand euro):

- Company logo of the sponsor appears on the event flyer.
- Company logo of the sponsor appears on the event promoting websites of Photonics4All and OptecNet.
- Reference as sponsor in all invitations by email and in all press releases of OptecNet Deutschland e.V., which will be published relating to the Photonics4All Start-up Challenge.
- Mentioning during the Photonics4All Start-up Challenge at the fair micro photonics 2016.

Daniela Reuter
Chair of the board
OptecNet e.V.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 644606.

Annex 4: Sponsorship agreement 2500

Pro rata Sponsorship agreement of
„Photonics4All Start-up Challenge“
as part of the fair “micro photonics” on October 11th-13th, 2016 in Berlin.

between (organizer):

OptecNet Deutschland e.V.
Garbsener Landstr. 10
D-30419 Hannover

and (sponsor):

The sponsor receives the following services in return for a pro rata sponsorship in amount of 2,500.00 Euro (two thousand five hundred euro):

- Company logo of the sponsor appears on the event flyer.
- Company logo of the sponsor appears on the event promoting websites of Photonics4All and OptecNet.
- Reference as sponsor in all invitations by email and in all press releases of OptecNet Deutschland e.V., which will be published relating to the Photonics4All Start-up Challenge.
- Mentioning during the Photonics4All Start-up Challenge at the fair micro photonics.
- Advertising material and one Rollup-Display of the sponsor in the event location during the Photonics Start-up Challenge on the fair micro photonics 2016.

Daniela Reuter
Chair of the board
OptecNet e.V.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 644606.

Annex 5: Sponsorship agreement 5000

Pro rata Sponsorship agreement of
„Photonics4All Start-up Challenge“
as part of the fair "micro photonics" on October 11th-13th, 2016 in Berlin.

between (organizer):

OptecNet Deutschland e.V.
Garbsener Landstr. 10
D-30419 Hannover

and (sponsor):

The sponsor receives the following services in return for a pro rata sponsorship in amount of 5,000.00 Euro (five thousand euro):

- Company logo of the sponsor appears on the event flyer.
- Company logo of the sponsor appears on the event promoting websites of Photonics4All and OptecNet.
- Reference as sponsor in all invitations by email and in all press releases of OptecNet Deutschland e.V., which will be published relating to the Photonics4All Start-up Challenge.
- Mentioning during the Photonics4All Start-up Challenge at the fair micro photonics 2016.
- Advertising material and one Rollup-Display of the sponsor in the event location during the Photonics Start-up Challenge on the fair micro photonics 2016.
- The possibility to be a member of the jury for the Photonics4All Start-up Challenge at the fair micro photonics 2016.

Daniela Reuter
Chair of the board
OptecNet e.V.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 644606.

THE PHOTONICS4ALL PROJECT IS PART OF THE OPTICNET

Annex 6: Promotion Flyer

Premium Sponsor

3D Printing on the Microscale Scale

Sponsors

Media Partner

PHOTONICS PUBLIC PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP

Photonics4All has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 644636.

Photonics4All
Discover the Power of Light

Photonics4All is a European outreach project, funded by the European Commission to promote photonics and light based technologies throughout the EU.

www.photonics4all.eu

Organizer

Innovation Networks for Optical Technologies

OptecNet Deutschland e.V.
Garbsener Landstraße 10
30419 Hannover
Germany
www.optecnet.de

Represented by

Photonics BW e.V. Anton-Huber-Straße 20 73430 Aalen Germany info@photonicsbw.de www.photonicsbw.de	OpTecBB e.V. Rudower Chaussee 25 12489 Berlin Germany optecbb@optecbb.de www.optecbb.de
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Start-UP

EUROPEAN PHOTONICS START-UP CHALLENGE

The stepping stone for your business!

Final pitch event at the international exhibition micro photonics Berlin, 13 October 2016

Photonics4All
Discover the Power of Light

Do you have an outstanding business model with innovative applications in the field of optical technologies?

Aim of the European Photonics Start-up Challenge

Support start-up companies and entrepreneurship in the field of photonics

- **STEPPING STONE** for outstanding business models, innovative technologies and service concepts
- **PROMOTION** of your business model throughout Europe
- **NETWORKING** in the photonics sector and contact to potential customers thanks to regional & national clusters
- **CONTACTS** with investors

Who can participate?

Applications are open to representatives of start-up projects, service providers and business representatives whose companies are younger than 3 years, generate less than 1 million euros in annual sales in photonics and for those the EU small business regulation applies.

Awards for the winner

4,000 Euros

Coaching package with a value of 1,500 Euros – redeemable in the leading photonics markets of Germany, France, Sweden, Austria or the UK

Exclusive professional article in the journal "Photonik"

Broad European-wide reporting in photonics related journals as well as on project and partner websites & social media

Awards for every start-up as finalist

Travel costs up to 300 Euros per start-up

Three-day trade fair presentation at micro photonics 2016 in Berlin

Free one-year membership in the corresponding photonics network in Germany, France, Sweden, Austria or in the UK

Business- and Technology Center Berlin Adlershof Tour on 14 October in Berlin

Application

Application deadline is 9 September 2016. Further information and application form on <http://photonicsbw.de/challenge>. Maximum of eight finalists will be notified on 19 September 2016.

Marketing Pitches

The final will take place on 13 October 2016 at the exhibition micro photonics in Berlin.

Every finalist presents the business idea / model within 3 slides in 3 minutes on a stage to the public audience and the jury. Subsequently the jury will have 5 minutes for questions.

The jury consists of five company representatives and cluster managers. The jury votes on the award (majority decision).

Selection criteria

- Technical performance
- Business idea
- Investment potential
- Competitive advantage
- Pitch performance

Annex 7: Promotion Flyer Update Handout

Premium Sponsor

3D Printing on the Molecular Scale

Sponsors

Messe Berlin

Berlin Partner
für Wirtschaft und Technologie

Berlin Adlershof

Media Partner

PHOTONICS PUBLIC PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP
Photonics4All has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 644606.

Discover the Power of Light

Photonics4All is a European outreach project, funded by the European Commission to promote photonics and light based technologies throughout the EU.

www.photonics4all.eu

Organizer

Innovation Networks for Optical Technologies

OptecNet Deutschland e.V.
Garbsener Landstraße 10
30419 Hannover
Germany
www.optecnet.de

Represented by

Photonics BW e.V. Anton-Huber-Straße 20 73430 Aalen Germany info@photonicsbw.de www.photonicsbw.de	OptTecBB e.V. Rudower Chaussee 25 12489 Berlin Germany optecbb@optecbb.de www.optecbb.de
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Start-UP

EUROPEAN PHOTONICS START-UP CHALLENGE

The stepping stone for your business!

Final pitch event at the international exhibition micro photonics Berlin, 13. October 2016, 13:00 - 16:00
Hall 7.2c, Career Lounge

Photonics4All
Discover the Power of Light

Meet the Finalists and see Innovative Business Models and Opportunities for Co-operations and Investments in Photonics!

Aim of the European Photonics Start-up Challenge

Support start-up companies and entrepreneurship in the field of photonics

- **STEPPING STONE** for outstanding business models, innovative technologies and service concepts
- **PROMOTION** of your business model throughout Europe
- **NETWORKING** in the photonics sector and contact to potential customers thanks to regional & national clusters
- **CONTACTS** with investors

More Information:
<http://photonicsbw.de/challenge/>

Awards for the winner

4,000 Euros

Coaching package with a value of 1,500 Euros – redeemable in the leading photonics markets of Germany, France, Sweden, Austria or the UK

Exclusive professional article in the journal 'Photonik'

Broad European-wide reporting in photonics related journals as well as on project and partner websites & social media

Awards for every start-up as finalist

Travel costs up to 300 Euros per start-up

Three-day trade fair presentation at micro photonics 2016 in Berlin

Free one-year membership in the corresponding photonics network in Germany, France, Sweden, Austria or in the UK

Business- and Technology Center Berlin Adlershof Tour on 14 October in Berlin

8 Finalists

Aixemtec, Germany
Asaphus Vision GmbH, Germany
Cristalline Mirror Solutions GmbH, Austria
GreenTropism, France
Lilian Labs, Germany
mirSense, France
Sicoya GmbH, Germany
TeraTonics, France

Marketing Pitches

The final will take place on 13 October 2016 at the exhibition micro photonics in Berlin.

Every finalist presents the business idea / model within 3 slides in 3 minutes on a stage to the public audience and the jury. Subsequently the jury will have 5 minutes for questions.

The jury consists of five company representatives and cluster managers. The jury votes on the award (majority decision).

Selection criteria

- Technical performance
- Business idea
- Investment potential
- Competitive advantage
- Pitch performance

Annex 8: Programme Handout

EUROPEAN PHOTONICS START-UP CHALLENGE

The stepping stone for your business!

Date: 13. October 2016, 13:00 - 16:00

Location: Messe Berlin, micro photonics, career lounge, hall 7.2c

Registration: http://optecbb.de/lang/de/anmeldung_20161013_startup.php

Program

13:00 – 13:15	Welcome, OptecNet, Photonics4All Project Dr. Frank Lerch, OpTecBB Johannes Verst, Photonics BW	
13:15 – 13:25	Pitch 1: Sicoya GmbH (Germany)	High-speed Silicon Photonics interconnects in next generation data centers
13:25 – 13:35	Pitch 2 TeraTonics (France)	Terahertz Sensing
13:35 – 13:45	Ref. 1 HTGF and possibilities for Start-ups Lucille Bonnet (HTGF)	
13:45 – 13:55	Pitch 3 Lilian Labs (Germany)	Water analysis device for everyone
13:55 – 14:05	Pitch 4 mir sense (France)	Laser based gas sensors
14:05 – 14:15	Ref. 2 WISTA and the Special Services for Start-ups Lars Hansen (Head of Charlottenburger Innovations-Centre (CHIC))	
14:15 – 14:25	Pitch 5 Asaphus Vision GmbH (Germany)	Develop embedded face recognition and gaze estimation software
14:25 – 14:35	Pitch 6 GreenTropism (France)	Mathematical models and software components for biospectral analyses
14:35 – 14:45	Ref. 3 Starting a Photonics Company Dr. Jürgen Schmied (GATTAquant GmbH)	
14:45 – 14:55	Pitch 7 AIXEMTEC GmbH i.G. (Germany)	Automation and assembly of optical systems
14:55 – 15:05	Pitch 8 Crystalline Mirror Solutions GmbH (AT)	AlGaAs-based multilayers, in high-performance laser optics
15:05 – 15:20	Ref. 4 Founding and Financing High-Tech Start-ups Prof. Rust (Mock Rechtsanwälte)	
15:20 – 16:00	Award ceremony/photo etc. and Get Together	

Sponsors and supporters:

Annex 9: Innovation Offers and Requests

Open Innovation

Find partners to penetrate new markets.

You are looking for a new solver or a partner to turn your idea into a new product?
Just fill in the formula and we will find an European partner for your innovative project.

Personal Data

Surname	First name
Company (if necessary)	
Address	
Zipcode, City	
Web	
Cell	
email	

Describe your Request Offer

Title
Innovation proposal - Please describe your innovation and its development status (Idea/concept; Project already started; Prototype; Serial production; ...) or what technology you are looking for. Be as precise as possible and give high quality of information.

Property right

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Patent registration | <input type="checkbox"/> Copy right |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Patent granted | <input type="checkbox"/> Exclusive right |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Design right | <input type="checkbox"/> Secret know-how |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Unprotected | <input type="checkbox"/> Property right |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Others: | |

Type of partnership

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Commercial agency agreement | <input type="checkbox"/> Manufacturing agreement |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Financial agreement | <input type="checkbox"/> Research cooperation agreement |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Joint venture agreement | <input type="checkbox"/> Services agreement |
| <input type="checkbox"/> License agreement | <input type="checkbox"/> Technical cooperation agreement |

Handling specification

- Publication on OptecNet Deutschland e.V.- and Photonics4All-Website as well as on events (e.g. workshops, international trade fairs).
- Consideration of the following Non-Disclosure Agreement. We contact you before divulging any information.

Non-Disclosure Agreement

The following agreement is hereby concluded between the representative of the Photonics4All consortium¹

OptecNet Deutschland e.V.
Garbsener Landstr. 10
D-30419 Hannover

and the client (person/company/institution mentioned under 'personal data').

In this agreement, the term "confidential information" refers to all verbal or written information and materials that OptecNet Deutschland e.V. directly or indirectly receives from the client for the completion of the request/offer and that are labelled as confidential due to their subject matter or other circumstance.

OptecNet undertakes to treat all confidential information of which it becomes aware as strictly confidential and to not use this information or disclose it to third parties without the prior written consent of the client.

OptecNet will take all suitable precautions to ensure the confidentiality of the information provided. Confidential information shall only be disclosed to consortium of the European project "Photonics4All". OptecNet will ensure that the project partners, who use the information have also sign this non-disclosure agreement before.

The obligation to maintain absolute confidentiality will also continue to apply after the end of the cooperation. Any documents provided, including all copies of these documents and any procedure documentation and materials, must be returned on demand.

OptecNet or the Photonics4All consortium shall be fully liable for all damages incurred by the client as a result of violation of these contractual obligations.

The non-disclosure agreement also applies to the legal successors of the parties. Any amendments or additions to this agreement must be made in written.

This agreement is subject to German law. The place of jurisdiction is _____.

¹ Photonics4All consortium (www.photonics4all.eu):
Steinbeis-Europa-Zentrum, OptecNet Deutschland e.V., University of Technology Delft, Opticsvalley Paris, University of Southampton, International Laser Centre Slovakia, Photonics Austria, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, PhotonicSweden

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 644606.

Annex 10: Report Draft PHOTONIK

European Photonics Start-up-Challenge

Im Finale der „European Photonics Start-Up-Challenge“ präsentierten acht europäische Photonik Start-ups in kurzen Marketing Pitches vielversprechende Geschäftsmodelle sowie innovative Technologien und Dienstleistungen.

Am 13. Oktober veranstaltete OptecNet Deutschland das Finale der „European Photonics Start-up-Challenge“ auf der Internationalen Fach- und Kongressmesse „micro photonics in Berlin“. Acht Finalisten aus Deutschland, Frankreich und Österreich präsentierten ihre Geschäftsmodelle den mehr als 50 Ausbesuchern und der fünfköpfigen Jury in drei Minuten mit maximal drei Folien.

Die Jurymitglieder: Isabelle Tournet (High Tech Gründerfonds Management GmbH), Jens Bille (Cube GmbH), Sylvia Kaschke (AIP-Real-Verlag GmbH), Olaf Krosch (Concept Optical Systems GmbH) und Dr. Beate Ludwig (Wista Management GmbH) beurteilten die

Marketing Pitches in den Kategorien Technische Leistung, Geschäftsfähigkeit, Investitionspotenzial, Wettbewerbsvorteil und Präsentation. Die Siwoya GmbH erhielt als Sieger einen Scheck über 6000 Euro sowie europaweite Unterstützung durch die Photonik Netzwerke. Siwoya bietet photonisch integrierte Transceiverlösungen in Silizium Photonik mit einem neuartigen Packagingkonzept für Datencenter. Zweitplatzierte wurde Crystalline Mirrors Solutions GmbH aus Österreich und Drittplatzierte nurSense SAS aus Frankreich.

Alle Finalisten, darunter neben der Erst- bis Drittplatzierten Aikomet, Anaphus Vision GmbH, Curo-Copticon SAS,

Die Gewinner der European Photonics Start-up-Challenge (Siwoya GmbH) (Mitte) und die Organisatoren Ingrid von Viet (Photonics BV) (links) und Dr. Frank Lohmeyer (rechts).

Löhner Labs und Teratronics, konnten sich während der drei Messetage präsentieren und erhielten eine kostenlose einjährige Mitgliedschaft im entsprechenden regionalen Photonik-Netzwerk.

Die European Photonics Start-up-Challenge wurde unterstützt durch den Premium Sponsor Nanoscribe GmbH sowie durch LUX Photonics Consortium, Berlin, Adlabs, Berlin, Patanz, Messe Berlin, EPIC und das Fachmagazin PHOTONIK. Die Start-up-Challenge ist eine Aktivität im Rahmen des von der Europäischen Kommission finanzierten Projekts „Photonics4All“, indem OptecNet Deutschland Partner ist.

www.optecnet.de
www.photonics4all.eu

Finale der European Photonics Start-up-Challenge auf der Messe micro photonics in Berlin. © Bild von der Webseite „Photonics4All“

FAQ Laserschutz

Lasert in Verbraucherprodukten – Damit Weihnachten nicht ins Auge geht

Darf ich zu Weihnachten meinen Vorgesetzten mit einem sehr hellen Projektor beleuchten der Laser Klasse 3R unbeaufsichtigt beleuchten?

Von einem Laser der Klasse 3R mit sichtbarer Laserstrahlung geht sowohl eine direkte Gefährdung der Netzhaut als auch eine indirekte Gefährdung durch Blendung aus. Als Folge sind bei direkter Bestrahlung bleibende Augenschäden oder Unfälle nach Blendung zu befürchten. Sie stellt sich die Frage, wie viele Personen, die das Grundstück betreten, vor den in der

Bedienungsanleitung genannten Gefahren schützen kann. Für den Postboten und die Freunde der eigenen Kinder die Bedienungsanleitung an die Postbox hängen? Ein Eintrabend zur Abgrenzung des Laserbereichs im Garten spannen und ein Laserwarnschild daran aufhängen? Und was ist mit der Blendung? Die Schäden Dritter nicht ausgeschlossen werden können, besteht für private Betreiber die Gefahr haftungsmässiger Konsequenzen. Darum ist zu empfehlen, den von der Bundesanstalt für Arbeitsschutz und Arbeitsmeri-

tin herausgegebenen „Übersichten Spezifikationen zu Lasern als 3R in Verbraucherprodukten“ zu folgen. Darin besagen, dass Laser in Verbraucherprodukten nur bis Laser Klasse 2M zulässig sind. Diese Spezifikation löst die Vermeidungswirkung gemäß § 5 (2) ProdSG aus, so dass Laser Klasse der 3R in Verbraucherprodukten faktisch verboten sind.

Lts: Zayous, T.ZH Laser Akademie GmbH
zayous@tzh-laser-akademie.de
www.tzh-laser-akademie.de